

THE ROLE OF KNOWLEDGE SHARING, TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP ON ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR (OCB) AND JOB SATISFACTION ISLAMIC SCHOOL TEACHERS

Mohzana*

Universitas Hamzanwadi, Indonesia

**Email: mohzana@hamzanwadi.ac.id*

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to analyze the relationship between transformational leadership on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), transformational leadership on job satisfaction, job satisfaction on OCB, knowledge sharing on OCB, knowledge sharing on job satisfaction. online questionnaire via social media to respondents. The respondents of this study were 378 Islamic teachers who were determined by simple random sampling. The questionnaire was designed using a Likert scale of 1 to 7. Analysis of research data used a structural equation model (SEM) with SmartPLS 3.0 software. The stages of data processing in this research are validity test, reliability test and hypothesis test. The independent variables of this research are the culture and commitment of sustainable schools; and the dependent variable is the performance of school employees. The results of this study are transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on OCB, transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on OCB, knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on OCB, knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction Islamic teacher.

KEYWORDS

Knowledge Sharing, Transformational Leadership, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), Satisfaction, Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Teachers

INTRODUCTION

Education in Indonesia has experienced quite rapid development. However, currently Indonesia is experiencing the Covid-19 pandemic which has an impact on the world of education. The teaching and learning process that should be running normally, like it or not, has to be carried out online. Schools and teaching staff are required to adapt to new habits. The development of education in Indonesia is currently in a period of testing. Even in the midst of a pandemic, what needs to be learned is how to respond to changing situations that force us as citizens to keep moving forward. Performance is a dimension that can be used to measure, evaluate in carrying out tasks in an organization/institution. Organizational success is largely determined by good human resource management. This should be the main priority of the organization to improve the performance of members of the organization. The performance of members is an important factor in the continuity of an organization, this is because whether or not the performance of a member of the organization affects the continuity of the next organization. Therefore, it is important for employees to develop extra-role behaviors, one of which is Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is a choice behavior that is not

part of an employee's formal work obligations, but supports the effective functioning of the organization. The existence of this behavior is expected to make the company more effective. An effective organization requires Organizational Citizenship Behavior so that employees are required to work not only on what is their job (in-role) but also able and willing to work outside of their main duties (extra-role) without being directly compensated in a formal reward or remuneration system. Job satisfaction is one of the reasons for increased employee performance, individuals who are satisfied with their work will have a commitment to the company and vice versa if the individual is dissatisfied with his job it is difficult to have a commitment to the company. Someone who has satisfaction at work will have a willingness to do more things beyond their formal responsibilities that create Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

Another factor that influences Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is the creation of knowledge sharing. Knowledge sharing is part of knowledge management. Knowledge management is a system that enables companies to take knowledge, experience and creativity of their employees for company improvement. There are three elements of implementing knowledge management, namely (1) knowledge creation, (2) knowledge sharing, and (3) knowledge application. Companies cannot create knowledge without the actions and interactions of their employees. This is where knowledge sharing is important as an element in knowledge management to provide opportunities for employees or members of the organization to share knowledge, experiences and ideas with other employees or members. Knowledge management (knowledge management), knowledge sharing is an important part that must be owned by the organization. Knowledge sharing is the key for organizations to be successful. Knowledge sharing is a systematic process of sharing, and distributing knowledge from one parties to other parties in need, through various methods and media. Knowledge sharing is a fundamental thing that must be done by employees in the organization to be able to contribute to the application of knowledge and innovation which ultimately leads to competitive advantage and can create Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) behavior among employees.

Ismail et al. (2011) stated that more and more organizations are changing their leadership paradigm to transformational from transactional leadership so that organizations can achieve their goals. Transformational leaders pay attention to the self-development needs of their followers, guide their subordinates to see and solve problems from a new perspective, and are able to motivate followers to achieve common goals by working harder. According to Adil et al. (2021) stated that an effective leader is one who gains the trust of his followers. According to Budur and Poturak (2021); Hamid et al (2022) stated that, one of the main reasons why followers are motivated by transformational leaders to perform beyond expectations is that followers trust and respect their leader Mohammad et al. (2011) examines empirical research which states that employee satisfaction is an important factor influencing OCB. According to Al-Mamary (2021) states that almost all transformational leadership research postulates that transformational leaders increase follower satisfaction, so satisfaction emerges as a potential mediator of the impact of transformational leader behavior on followers' OCB. According to Nurhidayati et al. (2021); Purwanto et al (2021); Singgih et al (2020); Trong (2017) Followers of transformational superiors have respect, loyalty, trust and admiration for superiors and are motivated to do OCB. The effect of transformational leadership on OCB is mediated by trust in

superiors and followers. Transformational leadership style has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Knowledge Sharing

According to Nurjanah et al (2020) Knowledge is the most important resource and the main source of an organization. Knowledge is an important factor in an organization to be able to compete in an increasingly competitive environment. Every individual in the organization must know how to use knowledge to increase competitive advantage for himself and others. Organizations must be able to take advantage of strengths and opportunities and understand weaknesses and threats in order to survive in competition. In order to utilize and develop knowledge, management is required with knowledge sharing activities. Knowledge sharing is one part of knowledge management in which a process of exchange of knowledge occurs between individuals within an organization/company. According to Nugroho et al (2020); Novianti (2021) When someone communicates their knowledge, other people assimilate that knowledge. The main focus of knowledge sharing is the ability of each individual to explain, code and communicate knowledge to other people, groups, and especially to organizations/companies. This process can occur between individuals in a team, between teams, between units in an organization, or even between organizations so that work productivity is higher. In sharing knowledge based on the experience gained by each individual, together it can be used to improve a thought or idea. According to Nurjanah et al (2020); Nugroho et al (2020); Novianti (2021) knowledge sharing motivates someone to want to share their knowledge. Through knowledge sharing, individuals process each other by exchanging their knowledge, both tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge, to create new knowledge.

Transformational leadership

According to Cho et al. (2022) transformational leadership is a process for achieving collective goals, through the unification of mutually beneficial motives owned by leaders and subordinates in order to achieve the desired change. Furthermore, Mastur et al. (2021); Pattnaik et al. (2021); (Mohzana et al., 2022) said that transformational leadership is a leadership behavior in which a leader uses his charisma to transform and revitalize the organization. These dimensions in transformational leadership can be described by Qurtubi et al. (2022); Istiqomah et al. (2021); Sefidan et al. (2021) Charisma, this dimension shows that a process by which a leader influences members by arousing strong emotions and identification with his subordinates. 2) Intellectual stimulation, this dimension shows that the process of a leader to increase the awareness of its members towards the problems around them and influence the members to look at these problems from a new perspective. 3) Inspirational, this dimension shows that the behavior of a leader stimulates the enthusiasm of its members for group tasks which can foster member confidence and ability to complete tasks and achieve group goals. 4) Consideration, this dimension shows a considerate behavior of a leader so that decisions and policies made have a sense of justice in the eyes of its members. 5) Individually oriented attention, this dimension shows that it provides support, encourages, and shares experiences about self-development to its members.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

According to Cho et al. (2022); (Wiflihani et al., 2020) defines OCB as individual behavior that is free (discretionary), which does not directly and explicitly receive rewards from the formal reward system, and which as a whole (aggregate) increases the efficiency and effectiveness of organizational functions. According to Sefidan et al. (2021) define OCB as behavior that is not part of an employee's formal work obligations, but supports the effective functioning of the organization. According to Purwanto et al. (2021) defines OCB as a form of someone's informal behavior beyond the formal behavior expected of them to contribute to the good of the organization and what is in it. Stanley (2013) states that OCB is characterized by efforts in any form that are carried out based on employee policies that provide benefits to the organization without expecting anything in return. Sudharma (2014) that this OCB behavior is free and voluntary, because this behavior is outside the formal job description. Free in the sense that the behavior is not a requirement that must be carried out in a certain role or a certain job description, or behavior that is a personal choice.

Job Satisfaction

According to Istiqomah et al. (2021); Sefidan et al. (2021) Job satisfaction represents negative and positive feelings from employees' perceptions of the work they face, namely a feeling to achieve and achieve success at work, high job satisfaction implies that employees feel happy and comfortable with the environmental conditions of the organization and receive rewards for their efforts his work. Job satisfaction is a positive emotional attitude of employees towards their work when compared to the remuneration they should receive according to their expectations. According to Qurtubi et al. (2022) Job satisfaction as the difference between what is expected at work and what is obtained. Job satisfaction is defined as a positive feeling about one's job which is the result of evaluating some of its characteristics. Job satisfaction is a feeling of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with employees at work related to their work in a company. Someone who is satisfied with his job will tend to behave positively towards the organization where he works. Job satisfaction is a very important factor that must be considered by an organization because job satisfaction determines the success of an organization.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research method is quantitative through surveys, data obtained by distributing online questionnaires via social media to respondents. The respondents of this study were 378 Islamic school teachers who were determined by simple random sampling. The questionnaire was designed using a Likert scale of 1 to 7. Analysis of the research data used structural equation modeling (SEM) with SmartPLS 3.0 software tools. The stages of data processing in this study were validity testing, reliability testing and hypothesis testing. The independent variables of this study were sustainable School culture and commitment; and the dependent variable is school employee performance.

The research hypotheses are:

H1: Transformational Leadership has a positive and significant effect on OCB

H2: Transformational Leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

H3: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on OCB

H4: Knowledge Sharing has a positive and significant effect on OCB

H5: Knowledge Sharing has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

Figure 1. Research Model

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity Test

Based on the results of data processing, the following are the results of the validity test in this study. In Figure 2, all question items have a factor loading greater than 0.7 and the AVE value for each variable is greater than 0.5, so no items are excluded. The results of the test show that all items from the instrument pass the convergent validity test.

Figure 2. Validity Test

After the phase 2 validity test was carried out, it was seen that all the constructs in the study were valid.

Reliability Test

To see the reliability results, it can be seen that the Average Variance Extract (AVE) value must be above 0.5 and the Composite Reliability must be above 0.7 (Purwanto et al, 2021). In this study the reliability test was carried out using two methods, namely Cronbach's alpha and Composite reliability. Cronbach's alpha measures the lower limit of the reliability value of a construct, while Composite reliability measures the actual value of the reliability of a construct. Composite reliability is considered better in estimating the internal consistency of a construct. Based on this opinion, this study uses Composite reliability to test reliability. The rule of thumb is that the alpha value or Composite reliability must be greater than 0.7 even though a value of 0.6 is still acceptable. Table 1 below shows the value of Cronbach's alpha and Composite reliability.

Table 1. Reliability Test

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Transformational Leadership	0.865	0.818	0.876	0.608
OCB	0.834	0.820	0.813	0.605
Knowledge Sharing				
job satisfaction	0.876	0.865	0.809	0.604

Based on Table 1, it is known that the AVE value is above 0.5 and the Composite Reliability value is above 0.7, so that all variables meet the reliability requirements. Table 1 above shows that the value of all variables in the reliability test using either Cronbach's Alpha or Composite reliability has a value of > 0.70, and validity testing using AVE (Average Variance Extracted) has a value of > 0.50. Therefore, it can be concluded that the variables tested are valid and also reliable, so that it can be continued to test the structural model

Hypothesis Test

To find out the effect between variables, the bootstrapping method is used. The bootstrapping approach represents nonparametric for the precision of the estimation. In the PLS method, the decision making to accept or reject a the hypothesis is based on the significance value (P Value), and the T-table value. In the SmartPLS application, the significance value can be determined by looking at the parameter coefficient values and the t-statistical significance values. The criterion for accepting or rejecting the hypothesis is if the significance value of the t-value is > 1.96 and/or the p-value is <0.05 at a significance level of 5% (α 5%) then H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected, otherwise if the t-value is <1.96 and/or the p-value > 0.05 at a significance level of 5% (α 5%) then H_a is rejected and H_o is accepted.). The following are the hypotheses proposed in this study:

Figure 3. Bootstrapping

The test results of all hypotheses shown in table 2 show that all hypotheses are accepted because they have a t-statistic value of more than 1.96 and a p-value < 0.05.

Table 2. Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis	T Statistics	P Values	Conclusion
Transformational Leadership on OCB	3.580	0.000	Supported
Transformational Leadership on job satisfaction	3.589	0.000	Supported
Job satisfaction on OCB	3.857	0.000	Supported
Knowledge Sharing on Job Satisfaction	5.392	0.000	Supported
Knowledge Sharing on OCB	3.677	0.000	Supported

The correlation of Transformational Leadership on OCB

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, the t value was $3,580 > 1.96$, so it was concluded that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on OCB. The research conducted by Nurjanah et al (2020); Nugroho et al (2020); Novianti (2021) which proves that transformational leadership style has a significant positive relationship to subordinate OCB. According to Nugroho et al (2020); Novianti (2021) transformational leadership has effectiveness different in various situations. Transformational leadership has a greater influence on smaller groups of followers than in complex organizations. According to Singgih et al (2020); Trong (2017) Transformational leadership is more effective when the leader can interact with employees and make decisions directly. This possibility is one of the factors that lead to the different findings in this study where transformational leadership is not able to directly influence OCB. According to Lin et al (2014); Nasra and Heilbrunn (2016) explains that transactional leadership behavior is found in the process of short-term exchange, or give and take between leaders and followers. According to Nurjanah et al (2020); Nugroho et al (2020); Novianti (2021) also states that managers consider both in-role and extra-role behavior when evaluating employee performance, managers also recognize employee achievements in both areas, in-role behavior as well as extra roles. This causes employees to see OCB performance as a means of obtaining recognition and appreciation, and this motivates employees to do OCB. This condition also happened at the Industrial Training Center, superiors will consider in-role and extra-role behavior when evaluating employee performance.

The correlation of Transformational Leadership on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the t value is $3,589 > 1.96$, so it is concluded that Transformational Leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. According to Lin et al (2014); Nugroho et al (2020); Novianti (2021) transformational leadership has a positive influence on job satisfaction. So it can be concluded that transformational leadership can be used as a basis for policies related to increasing employee job satisfaction in companies. Good leadership style will increase employee job satisfaction. Furthermore, Mastur et al. (2021); Pattnaik et al. (2021) said that transformational leadership is a leadership behavior in which a leader uses his charisma to transform and revitalize the organization. These dimensions in transformational leadership can be described by Qurtubi et al. (2022); Istiqomah et al. (2021); Sefidan et al. (2021) Charisma, this dimension shows that a process by which a leader influences members by arousing strong emotions and identification with his subordinates. 2) Intellectual stimulation, this dimension shows that the process of a leader to increase the awareness of its members towards the problems around them and influence the members to

look at these problems from a new perspective. 3) Inspirational, this dimension shows that the behavior of a leader stimulates the enthusiasm of its members for group tasks which can foster member confidence and ability to complete tasks and achieve group goals. 4) Consideration, this dimension shows a considerate behavior of a leader so that decisions and policies made have a sense of justice in the eyes of its members. 5) Individually oriented attention, this dimension shows that it provides support, encourages, and shares experiences about self-development to its members.

The correlation of Job Satisfaction on OCB

Based on the results of the hypothesis testing, the t value was $3.857 > 1.96$, so it was concluded that Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on OCB. Employee job satisfaction has a positive effect on OCB. Employees who are satisfied with their work have high OCB behavior, and vice versa. Employees who get job satisfaction will be motivated to do jobs that are not in their job descriptions. Intrinsic job satisfaction includes: a job that allows doing things different from time to time, jobs that are recognized in the community or community, jobs that match the skills possessed and extrinsic job satisfaction, including: the way superiors treat subordinates well, the ability of superiors to make good decisions, company regulations are strictly enforced, opportunities for self-development and opportunities to get promotions will increase the OCB of employees. According to Lin et al (2014); Nugroho et al (2020); Novianti (2021) Satisfied employees tend to talk about positive things about their organization, help other coworkers and try to achieve results beyond their job requirements, this is done because they want to give rewards for the good experiences they have had. feel . The results of this study are in line with; Nurjanah et al (2020); Nugroho et al (2020) that job satisfaction has a significant positive relationship with OCB. Krishnan et al. (2009) stated that extrinsic job satisfaction and intrinsic job satisfaction had a significant positive effect on staff OCB.

The Correlation of Knowledge Sharing and OCB

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, the t value is $5.3392 > 1.96$, so it is concluded that Knowledge Sharing has a positive and significant effect on OCB. The results of this study support previous research conducted by Lin et al (2014); Nugroho et al (2020); Novianti (2021) which resulted in Knowledge Sharing having a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). According to Dalkir (2005) there are three elements of implementing knowledge management, namely (1) knowledge creation, (2) knowledge sharing, and (3) knowledge application. Companies cannot create knowledge without the actions and interactions of their employees. This is where the importance of knowledge sharing as an element in knowledge management is to provide opportunities for employees or members of the organization to share knowledge, experiences and ideas with other employees or members. In knowledge management, knowledge sharing is an important part that must be owned by an organization. Knowledge sharing is the key for organizations to be successful . Lin et al (2014) states that knowledge sharing is a systematic process of sharing and distributing knowledge from one party to another who needs it, through various methods and media. Knowledge sharing is a fundamental thing that must be done by employees in the organization to be able to contribute to the application of knowledge and innovation which ultimately leads to competitive advantage and can create Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) behavior in employees

The Correlation of Knowledge Sharing and Job satisfaction

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, the t value is $3,677 > 1.96$, so it is concluded that Knowledge Sharing has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Research on knowledge management on employee satisfaction has been carried out well. However, there are several important notes that companies need to pay attention to in order to improve employee performance, as follows: Transparency in the performance appraisal system will greatly influence job satisfaction. From this system, employees can see their performance while working, without prejudice. This system should ideally be implemented at the start of recruitment, by providing any things that will be used as a measure in the performance appraisal process. In addition to salary, career path is closely related to employee motivation. However, this also greatly affects employee performance, especially employees who have worked for the company for years. This is starting to often not be used as a determining factor. Most companies currently only rely on newcomers. In fact, old employees have the potential to further improve their performance, as long as they are given time to attend workshops, seminars, or are given a study tour. Small or large company organizations must have job descriptions that have been determined by the company for each of its employees. But often, the division of labor is no longer suitable for the development of the corporate environment.

The analysis shows that employee job satisfaction mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and OCB. The better transformational leadership style can increase employee job satisfaction, so that it can improve employee OCB behavior. Based on the results of the analysis also shows that job satisfaction fully mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and OCB. The application of transformational leadership style is not able to influence OCB directly, but the application of transformational leadership style can influence employee job satisfaction and job satisfaction will affect OCB behavior. This research is in line with According to Nurhidayati et al. (2021) found that the effect of transformational leadership on OCB was indirect, mediated by job satisfaction. The same thing was also stated by Purwanto et al (2021) who found that job satisfaction was a mediator of the influence of transformational leadership on OCB.

The implications of the results of this study include two things, namely, theoretical implications and practical implications that emphasize the real benefits of research results to improve employee organizational citizenship behavior in Islamic school teachers. Through increased job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Some implications of the results of this study are factors related to organizational citizenship behavior in this study, namely job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Theoretical implications related to organizational citizenship behavior consistently strengthen previous theories that job satisfaction and organizational commitment affect organizational citizenship behavior of employees. In addition, the organizational commitment variable is able to mediate between job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior. The more employees feel job satisfaction, the more they will be able to increase their organizational commitment and the employee's organizational commitment has an important role in increasing employee organizational citizenship behavior. This is because employees who have organizational commitment to the company are employees who are satisfied with their jobs. This supports the research that has been disclosed in the research hypothesis, it can be concluded that research this supports and clarifies the

relationship between the variables of job satisfaction, organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior of Islamic school teachers.

According to Sefidan et al. (2021) revealed that the factors that play a role in the emergence of organizational citizenship behavior are job satisfaction, perceived fairness, employees' perceptions of the breadth of their work, as well as promotions and salary increases. Of the various factors mentioned above, one of the OCB factors, namely job satisfaction, still needs to be studied further because there is still question about its relationship with OCB. As stated by Purwanto et al. (2021); Qurtubi et al. (2022); Istiqomah et al. (2021); Sefidan et al. (2021) that industrial and organizational psychology psychologists are also interested in the question of whether job satisfaction is related to other aspects of work, such as attendance, OCB, and performance. Whether happy workers are more productive workers remains a matter of debate, as discussed in the critical controversies section. Connect (2011) has cited various research results, and said that from several previous studies, it was found that there were still differences in the findings between job satisfaction and OCB, so it still needs to be re-examined the relationship between the two variables. significant job satisfaction on OCB, and there is no relationship or no effect of job satisfaction on OCB. The results of the research on the relationship between job satisfaction and OCB were found by According to Pattnaik et al. (2021) showed that the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior was analyzed using multiple regression. Analysis using multiple regression was used to test the significance of the effect of the independent variables jointly on the dependent variable showing insignificant results.

The researcher advise teachers to conduct an analysis of learning evaluation questions before being tested in order to find out whether the questions are feasible to be tested. As well as suggesting teachers to determine teaching material based on student character and give an assessment according to the abilities of students. So as to produce satisfactory work and the performance provided will be optimal.

Based on the results of the questionnaire and statement items from the Knowledge Sharing variable, all teachers share knowledge based on the indicators that the authors have adopted. Researchers provide advice to teachers to hold discussions about work that is poorly understood with co-workers. As well as suggesting teachers to take notes New information/knowledge to share with colleagues. So that the relationship or co-worker relations are well established. Based on the results of the questionnaire and items statement of the Transformational Leadership Style variable, the authors provide advice to the principal in order to be able to provide a broad perspective to complete problem and provide direction to the teacher in order to complete a task. As well as suggesting that the principal treats each teacher according to their needs, different abilities and aspirations. Then it can convince the teacher that the school's goals will be achieved. Thus the leadership carried out by the principal can work well and produce good teacher performance as well.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study is transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on OCB,transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, job

satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on OCB, knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on OCB, knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of Islamic school teachers. Higher employee trust in superiors will increase employee OCB. Employee job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee OCB. The higher the job satisfaction felt by employees, the higher the OCB of employees. Employee trust to superiors mediates the influence of transformational leadership on OCB. Employee job satisfaction mediates the effect of transformational leadership on OCB. Transformational leadership does not have a direct effect on OCB, but has an indirect effect directly through employees' trust in their superiors and employee job satisfaction. Islamic schools pay more attention to the dimensions of transformational leadership, employee confidence in their superiors and the achievement of employee job satisfaction. Based on the results of this study, policy makers are expected to improve employee performance through extra role behavior or OCB. Theoretically, this research implies that transformational leadership style affects OCB indirectly. Indirect relationships can occur through mediation of employee trust in their superiors and employee job satisfaction, where someone will do OCB if the employee first believes in his boss and feels satisfied with his work, because someone who does not trust his boss and is not satisfied with his job tends to be lazy to do it. Employee trust in superiors has been proven to mediate the relationship between transformational leadership style and OCB, so management or the authorities are advised to be more selective in giving promotions to get officials who have competencies that are in accordance with their positions, have high integrity and have concern for their subordinates. In addition, officials or leaders whose competence is still lacking need to be improved through training. Job satisfaction has been proven to mediate the relationship between transformational leadership style and OCB, so that leaders or management is advised to pay more attention to aspects of job satisfaction, both intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction of employees. To deepen the study on OCB, it is also recommended for further research to examine each dimension of OCB

REFERENCES

- Adil, A., Kausar, S., Ameer, S., Ghayas, S., & Shujja, S. (2021). Impact of organizational socialization on organizational citizenship behavior: mediating role of knowledge sharing and role clarity. *Current Psychology*, 1-9.
- Arifiani, R. S., Sudiro, A., & Indrawati, N. K. (2020). the Role of Organizational Culture and Job Satisfaction in Mediating the Effect of Transformational Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *Jurnal Aplikasi Manajemen*, 18(3), 555-562.
- Al-Mamary, Y. H. S. (2021). The impact of transformational leadership on organizational citizenship behaviour: Evidence from Malaysian higher education context. *Human Systems Management*, (Preprint), 1-13.
- Budur, T., & Poturak, M. (2021). Transformational leadership and its impact on customer satisfaction. Measuring mediating effects of organisational citizenship behaviours. *Middle East Journal of Management*, 8(1), 67-91.
- Cho, C. C., & Kao, R. H. (2022). Developing sustainable workplace through leadership: Perspectives of transformational leadership and of organizational citizenship behavior. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 924091.
- Hamid, F. A., Widodo, S. E., & Buchdadi, A. D. (2022). The Influence of Transformational Leadership, Emotional Intelligence, Organizational Climate, and Teamwork, Towards

- Organizational Citizenship Behavior of Civil Servants. *International Journal for Applied Information Management*, 2(3), 26-39.
- Hapsari, D., Riyanto, S., & ENDRI, E. (2021). The Role of transformational leadership in building organizational citizenship: The civil servants of Indonesia. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(2), 595-604.
- Istiqomah, S., & Riani, A. L. (2021). Linking Transformational Leadership to OCB in Hospitality Industry: the Mediating Influence of Affective Commitment and Work Engagement. *JDM (Jurnal Dinamika Manajemen)*, 12(1), 53-67.
- Lin, R. S. J., & Hsiao, J. K. (2014). The relationships between transformational leadership, knowledge sharing, trust and organizational citizenship behavior. *International journal of innovation, management and technology*, 5(3), 171.
- Mastur, M., Soim, S., Haryanti, N., & Gufron, M. (2022). The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in Islamic Educational Institutions. *Al-Tanzim: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 6(3), 948-961.
- Mohzana, M., Fahrurrozi, M., & Murcahyanto, H. (2022). The Effect of Leadership and Work Motivation on Operator Performance. *AL-ISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 14(2). <https://doi.org/10.35445/alishlah.v14i2.2023>
- Nasra, M. A., & Heilbrunn, S. (2016). Transformational leadership and organizational citizenship behavior in the Arab educational system in Israel: The impact of trust and job satisfaction. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 44(3), 380-396.
- Nurjanah, S., Pebianti, V., & Handaru, A. W. (2020). The influence of transformational leadership, job satisfaction, and organizational commitments on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in the inspectorate general of the Ministry of Education and Culture. *Cogent Business & Management*, 7(1), 1793521.
- Nugroho, B. S., Suheri, S., & Hakim, L. (2020). Effect of Knowledge Sharing dan Leader member Exchange (LMX) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) to Indonesian Lecturers' Performance. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(9), 972-981.
- Novianti, K. R. (2021). Does Organizational Commitment Matter? Linking Transformational Leadership With Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Ocb). *Jurnal Aplikasi Manajemen*, 19(2).
- Nurhidayati, A. N., Susita, D., & Sebayang, K. D. A. (2021). The Effect of Transformational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Justice on Organizational Citizenship Behavior With Job Satisfaction as Intervening Variable. *The International Journal of Social Sciences World (TIJOSSW)*, 3(2), 193-204.
- Purwanto, A., Purba, J. T., Bernarto, I., & Sijabat, R. (2021). Effect of transformational leadership, job satisfaction, and organizational commitments on organizational citizenship behavior. *Inovbiz: Jurnal Inovasi Bisnis*, 9(1), 61-69.
- Singgih, E., Iskandar, J., Goestjahjanti, F. S., Fahlevi, M., Nadeak, M., Fahmi, K., ... & Purwanto, A. (2020). The role of job satisfaction in the relationship between transformational leadership, knowledge management, work environment and performance. *Solid State Technology*, 63(2s).
- Trong Tuan, L. (2017). Knowledge sharing in public organizations: The roles of servant leadership and organizational citizenship behavior. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 40(4), 361-373.

- Pattnaik, S. C., & Sahoo, R. (2021). Transformational leadership and organizational citizenship behaviour: the role of job autonomy and supportive management. *Management Research Review*, 44(10), 1409-1426.
- Purwanto, A., Purba, J. T., Bernarto, I., & Sijabat, R. (2021). Effect of transformational leadership, job satisfaction, and organizational commitments on organizational citizenship behavior. *Inovbiz: Jurnal Inovasi Bisnis*, 9(1), 61-69.
- Qurtubi, A. (2022). The Effects Of Transformational Leadership And Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Ocb) On Islamic School Teachers' Satisfaction. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(7), 2744-2753.
- Sefidan, S., Pramstaller, M., La Marca, R., Wyss, T., Roos, L., Sadeghi-Bahmani, D., ... & Brand, S. (2021). Transformational Leadership, Achievement Motivation, and Perceived Stress in Basic Military Training: A Longitudinal Study of Swiss Armed Forces. *Sustainability*, 13(24), 13949.
- Wiflihani, W., Juliaans Eliezer Rulland Marantika, M., Hery Winoto Tj, H., Dicky Hendrawan, D., Pradana Chairy Azhar, A., & Mohzana, M. (2020). The Organization and Management of National Education System. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7.